

D4.2 Code of Conduct

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

CoC	Code of Conduct
DEI	Diversity, Equity and Inclusion
ECR	Early Career Researcher
FPIC	Free, Prior, Informed Consent
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
ICC	Inuit Circumpolar Council
PMG	Project Management Group
UN	United Nations
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

As a common endeavor between different actors – academic institutions, industry, non-profit organizations and case study communities – research includes both direct and indirect collaborations. To realise the research integrity of this process within the ICEBERG project, this Code of Conduct (CoC) is intended as a framework for self-regulation — a starting point for the consortium to enhance the quality of its work and adapt throughout the project’s life cycle.

The first version of the ICEBERG CoC was led by Women of the Arctic and developed by Work Package 4 (WP4) of the ICEBERG project. Women of the Arctic (ry) is a Finland-based non-profit association focused on women and gender-related issues in the Arctic. WP4 members who participated in the elaboration of the CoC include team members from the Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC), the Helmholtz-Zentrum für Umweltforschung GmbH (UFZ), the Arctic Centre at the University of Lapland (ULAP), and Women of the Arctic (WoA).

To better understand the consortium and what we wish to gain from a living Code of Conduct we have employed a variety of methods. Consortium members participated in surveys, meetings, and workshops that informed preliminary versions of this CoC document. These surveys included a stakeholder mapping led by BSC; a series of workshops led by ULAP to develop a timeline of the flow of information within the project; a survey, led by the Research Institute for Sustainability – Helmholtz Centre Potsdam (GFZ), to determine partner’s approaches to methods, ethics, diversity, equity, and inclusion; and a survey, led by WoA, to identify the composition of the consortium. Additionally, in April 2024, the WP team organised an internal, consortium-wide workshop to develop co-production methods, co-develop a Code of Conduct for diverse, equitable, and inclusive research, co-develop a citizen science framework, and contribute to an ethics evaluation framework. The half-day event included presentations and interactive polls, surveys and mapping exercises. Participation was voluntary in all activities.

Subsequent versions of the CoC benefitted from the generous feedback of the Project Management Group (PMG), Advisory Board Members, Project Scientific Coordinator and Project Manager. We sincerely thank everyone who has participated in the process and encourage project and community partners to document their concerns, comments, and ideas at iceberg-wp4@lists.oulu.fi.

The CoC will be a living document that consortium members will periodically revisit and adjust to the dynamic nature of the project. These meetings will take place virtually, following the completion of field site visits, and in-person at the General Assembly meetings. Versions of the document will be saved internally so that changes in the document can be traced and referenced throughout the project.

2 Code of Conduct

Generally, a CoC is an adopted statement that sets guidelines regarding the norms, rules and responsibilities of a particular organisation. It usually goes beyond what is required by law and can either be compliance or value based. Often it covers issues related to workplace culture and behaviour (such as dress codes, conflicts of interest, or confidentiality), but it also contributes significantly in dealing with ethical issues.

The ICEBERG Code of Conduct is a value-based document that was informed by literature on knowledge co-production, ethics, diversity, equity and inclusion, and citizen participation, and developed through an iterative process that employed a variety of methods. The CoC builds on elements of the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (ALLEA 2023), a document that is "recognised by the EC as the primary standard for upholding research integrity across all research projects funded by the European Union" (ALLEA 2024, para. 2) and one that all project partners adhere to. While there are global and regional frameworks, such as the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, for scientific collaboration and the inclusion of historically marginalised groups, it is also important for the consortium to reflect on research integrity within the ICEBERG project. This is a unique opportunity for the project to build, and contribute to, a more inclusive polar research community that is enriched by a diversity of individuals, ideas, and approaches while addressing overlapping and interconnected barriers to equality (Seag et al. 2019). These barriers include age, care-giving responsibility, (dis)ability, ethnicity, gender identity, indigeneity, language, sexual orientation and socio-economic status. For instance, informal barriers to gender equality, such as gender bias and discrimination, have been pervasive in polar research since the advent of early expeditions. Their "gendered and colonial roots laid the foundation for polar science as we know it today (Bloom 1993; Glasberg 2012; Rosner 2009)" (Seag et al. 2019, 1) and, in some cases, continue to persist, such as in the context of fieldwork. Furthermore, recognising that many of our project members are guests in the project's designated field sites — in Svalbard; Husavik and Akureyri in Iceland; and Qaqortoq and Narsaq in South Greenland — and on Indigenous lands and waters, it is crucial that we are aware of the historical context of the areas in which we will conduct fieldwork.

The ICEBERG CoC is a concise, overarching, living document that project members can reference, revise, and enhance as the project develops. It seeks to provide guidance through short, clear and accessible statements on internal and external research collaboration based on the concepts of fairness, respect, care and honesty. It also includes a range of resources (see Annex) to support the code and researchers in the project.

With this approach the project seeks to focus on tailored improvements that can amplify diverse voices and contributions, as well as account for developments in data management practices, and provide space for course-correction based on input from the project's ethics advisor.

Moreover, as members of the ICEBERG project and the broader polar research community, the ICEBERG CoC seeks to advance existing efforts by integrating a designated work package that specifically focuses on addressing and tracing efforts to enhance knowledge co-creation and co-production; stakeholder engagement; diversity, equity and inclusion; citizen participation; and management of citizen data throughout the full life cycle of the project.

3 Who We Are

ICEBERG is an international project that takes a transdisciplinary and cross-cultural approach to research on marine pollution and climate change in communities in the European Arctic. Our consortium members represent ten different nationalities, based at 16 partner institutions including universities, research institutes, SMEs, non-governmental organisations and a communications agency. A majority of our consortium is female, with a majority of ICEBERG researchers coming from the natural sciences, and the rest self-identifying as interdisciplinary researchers and social scientists. As such, we cover a wide spectrum of research levels; including Early Career Researchers, Senior Researchers/Scientists, Research Leads and Directors. Although some, including the leadership, in the ICEBERG project have significant and long-standing previous experiences working in similar interdisciplinary and/or Arctic projects, it is a novel experience for others in the consortium.

3.1 Principles

The work of the ICEBERG project is guided by the following principles, identified during an internal project workshop:

- **Collaboration:** Collective activities with mutual goals that involve everyone, including partners and stakeholders, early on in the development of the work.
- **Zero Pollution:** A toxic-free environment achieved through the reduction of air, water and soil pollution to levels that are no longer considered to be harmful to human health and natural ecosystems, respecting the earth's boundaries (see [EU's Zero Pollution Action Plan](#)).
- **Inclusion:** The practice of providing equal access and opportunities to researchers in the project who may otherwise be excluded or marginalized.
- **Co-Creation:** Participatory collaborative research, including between the project's natural and social scientists, various technologies and (Indigenous and non-Indigenous) case study communities (ICEBERG takes a normative approach to the interchangeable concepts of co-creation, co-production and co-design).

4 Good Research Practices

The following sections cover good research practices for internal and external research collaboration framed through the concepts of fairness, respect, care, and honesty.

4.1 Fairness

- Ensure mutually beneficial co-production outcomes. Indigenous Peoples and local communities should receive tangible benefits from any research that is about, or which occurs on, their homelands. Research topics should satisfy the questions put forward by Indigenous Peoples and communities in addition to those put forward by science. Experts from different knowledge systems, with substantial leadership from Indigenous Peoples and local communities, must be involved when defining issues that will serve as the basis for ICEBERG's research.
- **Early engagement, trust building and long-term collaboration.** Ideally, research projects would not start their interactions with stakeholders from zero but would be based on long-term connections and trust. Case study communities must be involved from early on, first through the contact persons/local coordinators or intermediaries in the communities and then by repeated visits to the community for allowing the iterative trust-building process. In new projects and project locations, time, resources, effort and trustworthiness are needed for building trust. Within the project lifeline, participants from the case study communities should be given opportunities to provide input throughout the project, including in post-study feedback and evaluation, to ensure good participatory practices.
- **Ensure free, prior, and informed consent (FPIC).** Stemming from the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples (2007), FPIC is a basic requirement for the participation of Indigenous and other individuals, as well as Indigenous Peoples and local communities in research. In order to receive the free, prior, and informed consent of individual research participants in the project, research consent forms must be used and include information on the purpose of the project, descriptions of the type of activities, the potential risks and benefits of participation, the possible compensation for the contributions and the right to withdraw at any point without consequences. Moreover, the FPIC form should cover participants' wishes concerning anonymity and confidentiality (including photographs, videos, etc. from field sites). FPIC also includes the right to say no or maybe.
- **Include Indigenous and practitioners' knowledge equitably.** Indigenous People's knowledge systems include methods for seeking, analysing and validating information. Additionally, customary laws and unwritten protocols exist in each community around the sharing of knowledge (ICC 2022, Ellam Yua et al. 2022). When determining which methods to use and when, both Indigenous and scientific knowledge and methodologies should be equally considered, and there should be a consensus on the suite of methods that will be implemented. Identifying influential stakeholders who can become sponsors, intermediaries or contact points – in other words, committed individuals or groups who know the local language and can act as a link between social groups while also motivating others to participate – is key for effective interactions. Furthermore, identifying

intermediary agents, like community-based organisations, to monitor and ensure a power-balanced and transparent process is important to avoid the marginalisation of certain groups. It is also essential that Indigenous knowledge – as a knowledge system and cultural property – is equally appreciated as Western (natural, social and humanities) science. Other local cultural traditions, languages and values must also be respected.

- **Ensure the equal treatment of stakeholders in line with the rule of law.** Different methods, including new technologies (such as drones, time-lapse cameras), carry both risks and benefits. Project members should carefully plan how to promote equality of access and opportunity among stakeholders to avoid any inadvertent bias (whether its algorithm-based or training-based).
- **Establish mechanisms to compensate the participation of stakeholders.** Budget constraints have been identified as obstacles for knowledge co-production. Some scholars propose monetary compensation, since unlike scientists who are being paid to attend stakeholder meetings, stakeholders may be taking time away from their actual jobs or other sources of income. Ways to deal with stakeholder compensation in projects include the allocation of some of the project's budget for stakeholders to participate, or to acquire seed money to compensate for preparatory work, field work, and meetings with stakeholders (covering both travel and meeting costs). The outcomes that the project offers to stakeholders should also be put into value.
- **Ensure the proper attribution of the ownership of results.** Proper attribution of the ownership of newly generated results is important. Possible actions include co-authorship in publications, a memorandum of understanding outlining goals, principles and intellectual property rights, as well as the inclusion of stakeholder's organisations' names and logos in the acknowledgements. Furthermore, Indigenous knowledge must be acknowledged in the publications and not reported as new scientific findings. Researchers must also abide by any restrictions on publication (scientific or otherwise) negotiated during the community engagement phase; this may include embargoes on results or the non-publication of some or all results.
- **Agree upon information access, control and the required degree of confidentiality.** Guidelines for equitable access and control of information generated in a co-production of knowledge process must be agreed upon by all participants and be included in the project data management plan (D6.2). Moreover, the degree of confidentiality that individual stakeholders require must be confirmed with them on a case-by-case basis. This applies to both the information and views provided by participants, as well as how they are presented publicly in photographs. Anonymity must be granted to all participants unless agreed upon otherwise (through written consent). In the case of unfavourable research outcomes, participants should be protected from exposure to criticism.
- **Commit to the protection of citizens and their data.** Researchers in the project should draw on measures to protect citizens and their data throughout the research process. These include protocols and standards for the privacy and protection of citizen data; requiring informed consent for the use of participant data; ensuring fair representation and accessibility for all involved citizens; and ensuring intellectual property rights and attribution of their work. For instance, access to biological or agricultural resources, human biological materials, Indigenous knowledge, cultural artefacts, and non-renewable resources should be subject to FPIC; as should the data from any new technologies (e.g. face recognition technologies). Furthermore, any material or knowledge transferred to researchers within the project should be governed by formal agreements that are co-developed with the custodians of the resource and knowledge owners.

- **Agree upon culturally appropriate benefit-sharing with stakeholders.** Any potential monetary or non-monetary benefits should be clarified in advance and a culturally appropriate approach to benefit-sharing should be agreed upon, and regularly reviewed, with all relevant stakeholders.
- **Give key stakeholders the opportunity to review co-production outcomes.** Relationships between participants in the co-production process should be reciprocal rather than extractive. Results obtained through the research process should be shared and discussed with key stakeholders in a format that includes oral traditions and the use of Indigenous languages. All participants need to be open to different discussion formats, such as meeting for longer periods of time and participating in story-based discussion and problem solving. It is important to be aware that the Western scientific discourse may be perceived as aggressive, offensive, or confrontational to some Indigenous cultures that hold different conflict resolution and communication styles (Ellam Yua et al. 2022).

4.2 Respect

- **Comply with relevant codes, principles, guidelines and regulations.** To date, ICEBERG partners have shared 66 ethics-related sources and 61 references related to diversity, equity, inclusion and gender equality that they consider in their research process. These resources have been collated and are available to all partners in the ICEBERG project.
- **Adhere to ethical guidelines.** Research must follow relevant ethical guidelines, including the Ethics Management Plan of the ICEBERG project. These can be organisational, specific to Indigenous Peoples or fields of science. In Arctic research, these include e.g. the International Arctic Social Sciences Association (2020) principles, the Inuit Circumpolar Council (ICC) Ethical and Equitable Encounters protocols (ICC 2022) and Interagency Arctic Research Policy Committee (2018) principles. Ideally, agreeing on the ethical principles would be the starting point in the collaboration (Ellam Yua et al. 2022). When possible, research projects should seek the approval of a local ethics committee, located in the field site. The results of the ethics review should be respected by project partners.
- **Ensure open access data.** As agreed upon between the ICEBERG partners in the project's EU Grant Agreement, we commit to implementing the CARE and FAIR principles in citizen-collected data with an emphasis on people- and purpose-oriented data accessibility, adherence to metadata standards, and the adoption of open data formats (see the project's Data Management Plan). Where possible, datasets and results from the project should be published in open access repositories. Software/tools to view citizen-collected data should not be restrictive to facilitate the sustainability of the project and its tools beyond project end for continuous data collection processes.
- **Avoid causing research fatigue.** The project must respect the stakeholders' time and schedules including work calendars. Project actions must be well coordinated to avoid repeating the same questions or burdening the same individuals or organisations in the case study communities. As stakeholder engagement and social sciences data collection has increased in Arctic communities, so has the burden on some e.g. Indigenous Peoples and local communities. Participatory projects and other presence of researchers should be divided into several communities rather than the same ones. Hiring contact persons or liaisons at the case study communities saves time and effort of both researchers and the community members.

4.3 Care

- Avoid conflicts (participation of one stakeholder precluding engagement of another). Setting up a diverse group consisting of stakeholders from different sectors and interests is important, but it also involves being aware of possible conflicts of interests or power positions. The objectives of our project may evoke conflicting feelings for some stakeholders. For instance, while cruise ships are recognised by the ICC as causing pollution and disturbance in Greenland, they are also welcomed by some local communities as a source of income. And cruise ships may be negatively impacted if the results of a research project lead to policy changes, i.e. in the form of new restrictions.
- **Tailor risk management plan for researcher team.** To not expose researchers to health, safety and security risks, the research team should engage with its partner institutions and local partners to assess any potential risks and determine appropriate approaches for managing them. For instances, in cases where researchers in the project conduct citizen science or participatory research — and may thus cross professional boundaries — it is imperative that the researcher maintain research integrity standards and develop both a risk management plan for the researcher and a set of measures to safeguard participants (see below).
- Co-develop appropriate safety measures for stakeholders. In cases where an individual's participation in the project could lead, or contribute, to stigmatisation, incrimination, discrimination, or personal risk, the project should seek to co-develop measures for the safety and well-being of local stakeholders (e.g. through anonymity, confidentiality, agreements to not appear in media (e.g., photographs, videos...) used in science communication).
- **Consider environmental ethics.** Environmental ethics — although not fully distinct from interpersonal ethics — are an underdeveloped area of study in Western science that relates to how we ought to value, and behave in relation to, nature (Sandler 2018). Nature includes things that are not alive (such as bedrocks), alive but not sentient (such as plants), sentient but not human (such as animals), as well as collectives (such as species or ecosystems). Prior to, during, and after fieldwork, researchers should reflect on how they understand: (1) the relationship between themselves and the non-human environment that they engage with in their work; (2) the values that emerge from that relationship or are possessed by these entities (e.g. species, ecosystems, organisms, landscapes); (3) the principles, rules, or other guidance that these values justify; and (4) the implications of these principles and rules for how we should interact with the environment in which we work - now and in the future.
- **Aim for sustainable research design.** Considering whether the research might deplete local resources, or otherwise exacerbate existing environmental problems such as pollution (e.g. single-use plastics used in labs, project meetings) and climate change (e.g. high carbon footprint generated by travel) is important, as well as discussing concerns with the broader research team, local communities, stakeholders and other authorities to find an appropriate solution.
- **Follow the highest possible standard for environmental protection.** In cases where local environmental protection is inadequate, researchers should aim to follow higher standards in line with the codes, principles, guidelines and regulations followed by ICEBERG partners (see documents mentioned above). For instance, the use of technologies must contribute to, and not impede, existing environmental policies.

- Co-create processes for feedback, complaints, and misconduct to be heard. The project should work together with local stakeholders in each field site to co-create an accessible and genuine process for participants to share their concerns with the research process.

4.4 Honesty

- **Be transparent about the research process and the data that will be collected.** Research participants have the right to know about the decisions affecting them. It is thus important for the researcher to ensure that their research design and process are transparent, well-considered and clearly accessible to a layperson. For example, when it comes to data, it is essential to inform participants in the field site about how their data will be stored, used and potentially re-used; how to access and gain permission to use the data, metadata, protocols, code, etc.; how the data might be reused, and how it can be deleted in compliance with General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).
- **Co-develop a clear understanding of the collaborator's role.** Prior to field site visits, the research team and any collaborators should clarify the latter's role, responsibility and conduct throughout the life cycle of the project (research design, implementation, review, and dissemination). These conversations should also consider potential capacity building for local researchers.
- **Provide community members with the chance to participate in their own language.** Researchers should provide, as much as possible, translated written materials (e.g. brochures, website) and media publications (e.g. blog posts) in the languages of the case study communities to enable the equal participation of those who are not fluent in English. In the ICEBERG project, this means the translation of documents into Norwegian in Svalbard, Icelandic in Iceland, and into Greenlandic and Danish in Greenland. Researchers should also use interpreters during data collection, co-production (such as workshops, focus groups etc.) and public events (for the interpreting presentations and discussions). Interpreters can also give cultural advice. The translation of new scientific concepts to local languages is essential for ensuring meaningful participation. Researchers should also avoid the excessive use of scientific and technical terms when engaging with the communities and, when necessary, explain the terms being used. This also applies to communications between researchers coming from different fields of research in the project.
- **Invest time and effort into the science popularisation of research findings.** When possible, researchers should communicate the results of the project to case study communities, and other key stakeholders, in the local language of the field sites in an accessible format (e.g. news article, Facebook post) or through a field site visit.
- **Respect confidentiality.** Although researchers in the project should share their results in a transparent and honest way, confidentiality must be respected.

5 Building a Respectful and Ethical Research Culture

The ICEBERG project members commit to maintain a safe, welcoming, respectful, productive and trusted working environment for all consortium members and collaborating community partners; including researchers, management, staff, service providers and subcontractors. This includes the following commitments:

- to take responsibility for the project's research integrity;
- to encourage cross-pollination between disciplines through regularised meetings between WPs and within WPs;
- to monitor and adapt to changing expectations, standards, laws, regulations or potential cases of misconduct;
- to learn about their own institution's codes, principles, guidelines and regulations and develop the necessary skills (such as ethics training) to implement them;
- to bring in a diversity of voices when recruiting, organising meetings, workshops or panels;
- to be open, patient and listen. When in doubt, researchers should follow the WAIT technique ("Why am I talking?") to reflect on their intention;
- to have project leads, senior researchers, and supervisors mentor their respective team members and lead by example when it comes to structuring research activities;
- to assign active roles that advance Early Career Researcher's (ECRs) career development in project meetings, tasks and WPs without putting the onus solely on them;
- to ensure that their institution supports the appropriate infrastructure for data management and partakes in appropriate data stewardship over the course of the project;
- to use research funds conscientiously;
- to accurately and honestly communicate with colleagues in the project;
- to avoid jargon;
- to consult their collaborating colleagues and formally agree to the submission of a publication or other forms of dissemination exploiting the project's results;
- to formally agree on the sequence of authorship and, whenever possible, describe each author's responsibilities and contributions;
- to acknowledge the contributions of those (collaborators, assistants, funders) whose work does not meet the criteria for authorship;
- to encourage and acknowledge co-authorship across disciplines (natural & social sciences & humanities), research stages (ECR & Senior Researchers) and with community-members when relevant and consented to;
- to acknowledge Indigenous and traditional environmental knowledge;
- to disclose any financial conflicts of interest and sources of financial support;

- to issuing corrections or retracting publication, if necessary;
- to support the expectation that research team members will not be working outside office hours (considering consortium member's local time zone), on weekends, during public holidays and/or on personal vacation;
- to consider national and institutional practices and guidelines relating to holidays (e.g. related to summer vacation, winter holidays, etc.)
- to support flexible work, when possible;
- to make available teleconferencing during in-person meetings for those who cannot attend in-person, when possible.

6 Implementation

For the implementation of the CoC, the ICEBERG project relies on a self-regulatory approach to research integrity — one that is based on openness, transparency and mutual trust between researchers, institutional partners, and communities. Thus, in addition to the project’s Ethics and Data Management Plans, all ICEBERG partners are expected to have measures in place to monitor their adherence to the CoC. Project partners are also invited to state their adherence to the Code on their websites.

6.1 Violations of Research Integrity

The definition of violations of the ICEBERG project’s research integrity — including research misconduct such as falsification, fabrication, and plagiarism — and fair, consistent and transparent approaches to dealing with such allegations and violations follow the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity.

7 Continuous Evaluation and Improvement

The CoC will be a living document where we, as a consortium, will periodically revisit and adjust to the dynamic nature of the project. These meetings will take place virtually, following the completion of field site visits and in-person at the General Assembly meetings. During these meetings, the project will gather feedback from the consortium on how the CoC is serving the needs of its members. Versions of the document will be saved internally so that changes can be traced and referenced throughout the project.

Additionally, beyond revisiting the CoC, we will facilitate additional points of engagement – prior to and after field site visits – to revisit the project’s mapping of stakeholder groups, identify improvements to the consortium’s internal and external knowledge co-production methods (e.g. the use of drones), refine and develop the project’s framework for co-evaluation of ethics and engagement protocols, and reflect on the implementation of diversity, equity and inclusion (DEI) principles over the course of the project. Based on input from both researchers and community members, we will facilitate further interventions that foster dialogue and reflection in the ICEBERG consortium.

Finally, the project commits to identifying one or multiple ombudsperson(s) within the coming six months.

8 Annex: Key Resources

The WP4 team has compiled a syllabus of relevant literature for project beneficiaries grouped by theme, including knowledge co-production and co-creation, ethics, gender, DEI, citizen participation, data management, and networks. Additional documents will be added during the project's life cycle. Have suggestions for readings to include in the list? Email us at iceberg-wp4@lists.oulu.fi.

General Literature

ALLEA. (2023). The European Code of Conduct for research integrity - Revised edition 2023. Berlin. doi: <https://allea.org/portfolio-item/european-code-of-conduct-2023/>.

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Knowledge Co-Production

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